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Editorial

Spirituality, Wisdom and Courage

Coronavirus and COVID-19 have brought a flood of fear and uncertainty for many of us. We are forced to listen to 24-hour news cycle that terrifies us. We've been told not to leave our houses unless we must. Most of our lives are in sudden upheaval as we adjust to a "new normal" for an unforeseen amount of time. The uncertainty is unsettling.

Sometimes we don't know where to turn for support. We feel lost. While this global pandemic is unique in many ways, these feelings of fear and isolation are nothing new. We may remember that our religious and spiritual traditions have been poised to respond to times of crisis since time immemorial (St. Jude Children's Research Hospital, 2021).

Some common themes that emerged during this pandemic, especially the second wave are:

Grief: While we normally think of grief only in connection with the death of a loved one, we can have the same feelings of loss when we are facing uncertainty.

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We could all be grieving losses in this time. These may include loss of:

- Some of our own friends and relatives
- A “normal” daily routine
- Time with friends and family
- A feeling of we are in control of
- Spiritual community, sacraments, and prayers

Sometimes when we experience grief, we feel shocked, anxious, fearful, sad, powerless, angry, or helpless. What we need to remember is that all these feelings and many others are normal. Being able to acknowledge where we are emotionally and spiritually can be empowering.

Let us be kind to ourselves as we navigate through our emotions. We can remember that we are all together despite the distance we are forced to maintain.

Lord, knowing fully well that you are the Lord of this tragedy we experience, we surrender ourselves to you. We pray for all those who have died of this terrible sickness. As we grieve their parting, may we draw strength from your tragic death and glorious resurrection.

Prayer and Wisdom: Often in times of distress and pain, we turn our minds to God. This can be difficult if the places we normally go to worship are closed right now. It can be helpful to try to recreate this environment at home (St. Jude Children’s Research Hospital, 2021). Many houses of worship are posting services online. Let us participate in them and try to draw hope and strength for ourselves and those who are close to us. Let us use this chance to recollect ourselves and make our live deeper and wiser.

Courage and Hope: Recognising that things are bad, we cannot afford to close our eyes to the suffering and agony of all around us. While keeping our eyes wide open to their angst, can we also be sources of courage and hope? Though difficult, we can still spread awareness, attention and attentiveness, with courage and hope. We do know that things are very difficult. But we can still count on Him, who has gone through terrible betrayal and pain. We need to be cautious and courageous. Not fearful and frightened. Let us be catalysts of hope in these troubled times.

A simple prayer we can repeat is: Lord, knowing fully well that you are the Lord of this tragedy we experience, we surrender ourselves to you. We pray for all those who have died of this terrible sickness. As we grieve their parting, may we draw strength from your tragic death and glorious resurrection.

It is a terrible experience to imagine that we may not be there to touch the next issue of our journal. Still, life goes on! It must!

In this sense, we can draw wisdom from the wounds that we have been dealt with. We do know for sure that this too will pass away. We shall overcome. Together. Fear not, let us be courageous (Pandikattu, 2020), with the Lord who has suffered and risen!

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The Coronavirus Pandemic and Its Impact on Mental Health

Joseph M.D.

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Abstract: But according to scientists the Covid-19 pandemic is not just a medical phenomenon; it affects individuals and society and causes disruption, anxiety, stress, stigma, and xenophobia. A very serious aspect of the pandemic is that the behaviour of an individual as a unit of society or a community has marked effects on the dynamics of a pandemic that involves the level of severity, degree of flow, and aftereffects. Reflecting on mental health in pandemic one realizes that more than making a political or religious or economic issue out of the rising situation, the need of the hour is to cope with the mental state of us humans (Fox, 2020). Hence all people of responsibilities as medical scientists, psychologists and psychiatrists, of all fields to be empathetic and compassionate

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to humanity as all of us are placed in this situation irrespective of one's state of life.

Keywords: Covid-19 Pandemic, Mental health, Risk, Stigmatisation

The common understanding of pandemic is merely a medical phenomenon. But according to psychologists, a pandemic is not just a medical phenomenon; it affects individuals and society and causes disruption, anxiety, stress, stigma, and xenophobia. A very serious aspect of the pandemic is that the behaviour of an individual as a unit of society or a community has marked effects on the dynamics of a pandemic that involves the level of severity, degree of flow, and aftereffects (Javed et al., 2020). For example, the rapid human-to-human transmission of the SARS-CoV-2 resulted in the enforcement of regional lockdowns to stem the further spread of the disease. Isolation, social distancing, and closure of educational institutes, workplaces, and entertainment venues consigned people to stay in their homes to help break the chain of transmission. However, the restrictive measures undoubtedly have affected the social and mental health of individuals from across the board (Javed et al., 2020).

As more and more people are forced to stay at home in self-isolation to prevent the further flow of the pathogen at the societal level, governments must take the necessary measures to provide mental health support as prescribed by the experts. The psychological state of an individual that contributes toward community health varies from person to person and depends on his background and professional and social standings (Javed et al., 2020). Thus as human persons, we are segregated and alienated at this juncture, and more than ever before humanity is segregated and our interpersonal relationships are affected in space and time.

Studies tell us that quarantine and self-isolation can most likely harm one's mental health. A review published in *The Lancet* said that the separation from loved ones, loss of freedom, boredom, and uncertainty can cause a deterioration in an individual's mental health status (Javed et al., 2020). To overcome this, measures at the individual and societal levels are required. Under the current global situation, both children and adults are experiencing a mix of emotions. They can be placed in a situation or an environment that may be new and can be potentially damaging to their health (Javed et al., 2020). Some of the areas of risk groups that should be taken are the following;

Children and Teens at Risk

As we are in the pandemic, children, away from their school, friends, and colleagues, staying at home can have many questions about the outbreak and they look toward their parents or caregivers to get the answer. Studies tell us that not all children and parents respond to stress in the same way. For example, kids can experience anxiety, distress, social isolation, and an abusive environment that can have short- or long-term effects on their mental health. Some common changes in children's behaviour can be:

- Excessive crying and annoying behaviour, Increased sadness, depression, or worry
- Difficulties with concentration and attention
- Changes in, or avoiding, activities that they enjoyed in the past
- Unexpected headaches and pain throughout their bodies
- Changes in eating habits

To help offset negative behaviours, psychologists advise parents to remain calm, deal with the situation wisely, and answer all of the child's questions to the best of their abilities.

Parents can take some time to talk to their children about the COVID-19 outbreak and share some positive facts, figures, and information. Parents can help to reassure them that they are safe at home and encourage them to engage in some healthy activities including indoor sports and some physical and mental exercises (Javed et al., 2020). Parents can also develop a home schedule that can help their children to keep up with their studies. Parents should show less stress or anxiety at their home as children perceive and feel negative energy from their parents. The involvement of parents in healthy activities with their children can help to reduce stress and anxiety and bring relief to the overall situation (Javed et al., 2020).

Elders and People with Disabilities at Risk

In this situation, elderly people are more prone to the COVID-19 outbreak due to both clinical and social reasons such as having a weaker immune system or other underlying health conditions and distancing from their families and friends due to their busy schedules. According to medical experts, people aged 60 or above are more likely to get the SARS-CoV-2 and can develop a serious and life-threatening condition even if they are in good health (Javed et al., 2020 & Davis, 2015).

The consequences of Physical Distancing

Physical distancing due to the COVID-19 outbreak can have drastic negative effects on the mental health of the elderly and disabled individuals. Physical isolation at home among family members can put the elderly and disabled person at serious mental health risk. It can cause anxiety, distress, and induce a traumatic situation for them. Elderly people depend on young ones for their daily needs, and self-isolation can critically damage a family system. The elderly and disabled people living in nursing homes can face extreme mental health issues. However, something as simple as a phone call during the pandemic outbreak can help to console elderly people (Karimundackal, 2020). COVID-19 can also result in increased

stress, anxiety, and depression among elderly people already dealing with mental health issues (Ronald, 2020).

Family members may witness any of the following changes to the behaviour of older relatives, such as Irritating and shouting behaviour, change in their sleeping and eating habits, and emotional outbursts (Javed et al., 2020).

The World Health Organization suggests that family members should regularly check on older people living within their homes and at nursing facilities (Javed et al., 2020). Younger family members should take some time to talk to older members of the family and become involved in some of their daily routines if possible.

Health Workers at Risk

Dealing with the pandemic, doctors, nurses, and paramedics working as a front-line force to fight the COVID-19 outbreak may be more susceptible to develop mental health symptoms (Javed et al., 2020). Fear of catching a disease, long working hours, unavailability of protective gear and supplies, patient load, unavailability of effective COVID-19 medication, death of their colleagues after exposure to COVID-19, social distancing and isolation from their family and friends, and the dire situation of their patients may take a negative toll of the mental health of health workers. The working efficiency of health professionals may decrease gradually as the pandemic prevails. Health workers should take short breaks between their working hours and deal with the situation calmly and in a relaxed manner (Javed et al., 2020).

Stigmatization

Another cause of great concern is of people recently released from quarantine can experience stigmatization and develop a mix of emotions. Everyone may feel differently and have a different welcome by society when they come out of quarantine. People who recently recovered may have to exercise social

Health workers who try to save lives and protect society may also experience social distancing and changes in the behavior of family members!

distancing from their family members, friends, and relatives to ensure their family's safety because of the unprecedented viral nature. Different age groups respond to this social behaviour differently, which can have both short- and long-term effects (Javed et al., 2020).

Health workers who try to save lives and protect society may also experience social distancing, changes in the behaviour of family members, and stigmatization for being suspected of carrying COVID-19 (Javed et al., 2020). Previously infected individuals and health professionals (dealing with pandemic) may develop sadness, anger, or frustration because friends or loved ones may have unfounded fears of contracting the disease from contact with them, even though they have been determined not to be contagious (Javed et al., 2020).

Medical experts in mental health tell us that the current situation requires a clear understanding of the effects of the recent outbreak on the mental health of people of different age groups to prevent and avoid the COVID-19 pandemic (Javed et al., 2020). For this the following guidelines can be followed by every one of us as we are related to one another and responsible for one another:

- Understanding the effects of the COVID-19 outbreak on the mental health of various populations are as important as

understanding its clinical features, transmission patterns, and management.

- Spending time with family members including children and elderly people, involvement in different healthy exercises and sports activities, following a schedule/routine, and taking a break from traditional and social media can all help to overcome mental health issues.
- Public awareness campaigns focusing on the maintenance of mental health in the prevailing situation are urgently needed (Javed et al., 2020).

Conclusion

Reflecting on mental health in pandemic one realizes that more than making a political or religious or economic issue out of the rising situation, the need of the hour is to cope with the mental state of us humans (Fox, 2020). Hence all people of responsibilities as medical scientists, psychologists and psychiatrists, of all fields to be empathetic and compassionate to humanity as all of us are placed in this situation irrespective of one's state of life (Pandikattu, 2020). Therefore, no one is superior or inferior in this hour, we are mere fellow-servants of one another as one humanity, reminding us the teaching to 'love our neighbour as oneself.'

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The Blood of the Adivasi Martyrs

P. A. Chacko SJ

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Abstract: This article reflects on the Banjhi Massacre of 1985 and the martyrdom of Anthony Murmu, an ex-MP and ex-Jesuit, who had been working for the welfare of the Adivasis in Jharkhand. The martyrdom of Murmu has borne fruit. It also reflects on the hopes and aspiration of the Santal tribals in this region, which is the largest Adivasi group in India, with a population of 7,600,000.

Keywords: Santal Tribes, Anthony Murmu, Banjhi Massacre, Martyr

For the Adivasis (formerly called tribals or aboriginals) of Jharkhand, April 19, 1985, was a blood-drenched day. On that fateful day, their respected leader Anthony Murmu (1930-1985; affectionately called ‘Murmu Baba’) and 14 others were felled down by the combined force of non-tribal exploiters and the Sahibganj district administration in erstwhile Bihar. This article

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reflects on this incident, which took place 35 years ago. It traces the history and causes of this tragic event and draws some lessons and hope for today.

The Atrocity of 1985

The scene of the atrocity was Banjhi market, 20 kilometres from the district HQ of Sahibganj in Jharkhand. The 15 victims included Ex-MP Anthony Murmu, a 12-year-old boy and a scheduled caste person.

The prolonged exploitation of the tribal population by non-tribal moneylenders and traders coupled with land grabbing mafia went on unabated. The gullible Adivasis had become the target point of exploitation by Banjhi's business community which included Muslims and Hindus.

Extortionist money lending was rampant. It became a convenient route for moneylenders and petty traders to grab people's cultivable land from defaulters. The illegal timber trading in connivance with the corrupt forest department personnel caused depletion of forest cover. To add insult to injury, the timber mafia would stack their stolen timber on Adivasi land to avoid detection and to cunningly shift the blame.

The snobbish and derisive behaviour of the non-Adivasis towards the Adivasis by the exploiting community was keenly felt by the Adivasis. Tension was building up. The flicker that burst into a flame of anger and resentment was the suspected murder of Santal Adivasi Matru Murmu from a fish pond on March 25, 1985. He had gone missing for a week.

On a common fishing day, Moti Bhagat, a non-tribal, had instructed the Santals not to cast their net in one portion of the pond. Minutes later, Santals fished out the dead body of Matru Murmu from that very spot.

The Santals got agitated. Moti Bhagat disappeared through an escape route. The police were slow in taking action. Though inquest

was done, the body remained in the open for three days, preyed upon by dogs and birds and without post-mortem. No one was arrested and the police did not bother to conduct a proper enquiry. That again caused anger and revulsion among the people.

Three weeks later Some Adivasis, wanting to plough their land for cultivation, sought to get the illegally stacked timber from their land. Sadik Mia and other non-tribals, who had stacked such timber, resisted it by firing in the air to frighten the Santals. The firing went on for a long time (Sarkar, 2005).

The Santals could not stomach such highhanded action by the non-Adivasis. About 600 of them gathered outside the market for a meeting. The non-Adivasis sent a quick signal to the Sub-Divisional Magistrate (SDM) of Sahibganj that they were going to be attacked by armed Santals.

The SDM came with a police contingent. The Santals chose five of their representatives with Anthony Murmu as their leader to convey their grievances to the SDM. But the result turned out to be disastrous. Prompted by the rumour mongering non-Adivasis, the SDM ordered firing. The firing operation was done by the police force and the waiting money lenders with country guns. 14 people lay dead in the market area while Anthony Murmu was not seen anywhere. It was learnt later that Murmu's dead body was rushed to far away Bhagalpur district for post-mortem.

Murmu, the Martyr

An Ex-Jesuit, Murmu was at the time an Ex-member of the Parliament (Jose, 2021: 100f). Due to political compulsions to serve his people better for their welfare, he opted out into politics

Due to political compulsions to serve his people better for their welfare, he opted out into politics and became social activist for people's cause.

and became social activist for people's cause.

As a grassroots social activist, he had the people's cause at heart. He had an ear to the ground. He was a born singer. Equipped with musical and composing talents, he organised a cultural troupe and conducted animation programs in villages. His popular techniques gathered crowds and they imbibed his messages. He was their 'Murmu Baba'. The civil administration, fed with rumours from non-Adivasi community, had their eyes on Murmu.

After felling Murmu and others, a Commission of Enquiry was constituted by the then Bihar state government. Nothing came out of the Commission's findings. The unfeeling presiding judge who enquired into the atrocity gave a clean chit to the district administration and to the murderers. As if adding insult to injury, he made a tongue-in-cheek statement: 'It was a pity that so many people lost their lives.'

PUCL (Bihar) conducted its own enquiry. The team was headed by Dr. Prabhakar Sinha, Acting President, PUCL Bihar, and was assisted by Sri. Ravi Shankar Prasad, Advocate, Patna H.C., (current Law Minister in Modi government), Adv. Jawahar Prasad Karn, Patna H.C, and Dr. Shashi Bhushan, Social Scientist, A.N. Sinha Institute, Patna.

Their report spared no words in pointing out the collusion between the police and the traders in exploiting the Adivasis. It also pointed out that the Enquiry Commission ordered by the Bihar government was a pre-planned ploy to suppress the truth and to give a lean chit to the administration and the business community.

Late Advocate Basudeo Besra (1985) asserted that "the Commission was one-sided, government-controlled and a mock-opera. Its operation and findings were on pre-planned lines to cater to the dictates of the government. Such actions are totally unacceptable to the Adivasis."

Conclusion: Hopes and Aspirations of the Santals

The blood of the martyrs has given birth to a strong movement among the Adivasis of the area to free themselves from the clutches of money lenders and extortionists.

Through a slow and steady process of awareness building, initiated by NGOs like Sona Santal Samaj Samiti, the once victimized people have reclaimed their land and given a fitting burial to the notorious money lending system. The Jesuits of Dumka Raiganj province played a very supporting role in building up the Sona Santal Samaj Samiti.

Today self-reliance through saving schemes, cultivation of their own land and protection of the forest cover and self-rule through Panchayat Raj provisions are the priorities of the Adivasis of the area.

Today self-reliance through saving schemes, cultivation of their own land and protection of the forest cover and self-rule through Panchayat Raj provisions are the priorities of the Adivasis of the area.

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P.A. Chacko SJ is a Jesuit priest from Jharkhand, India. At present Director of Arrupe Tribal Cultural Centre, Bhignadih, Sahibganj District, Jharkhand. Mr. Anthony Murmu was personally known to the author of the article. The author visited the place of occurrence the next day and met the people affected by the firing. Was present all through the sessions of the Enquiry Commission. Email: chackoanthony827@gmail.com
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The Bewitching New Digital World and the Human Experience of Time

Victor Ferrao

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Abstract: The growing new digital world has changed our experience of time. Time today is not felt as irreversible and linear. We seem to be lost in an intensive now. We are mindlessly living in a now time. The moment has become intense and we are moving in all directions within the focal point of now. The arrival of the smart phone has amplified this experience of time. We have to make responses at the speed of a blink of an eye. This means it is difficult to offer a reflected or rationally considered responses to our condition. This is why this study proposes the adoption of reflexive responses through the cultivation of phronesis as well as embrace a habit that thinks what one does.

Keywords: Digital world, Electracy, Post-literacy, Time, Phygital, Phronesis, Communication-technologies

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The growing new digital world has changed our experience of time. Time today is not felt as irreversible and linear. We seem to be lost in an intensive now. We are mindlessly living in a now time. The moment has become intense and we are moving in all directions within the focal point of now. The arrival of the smart phone has amplified this experience of time. We have to give ourselves responses at the speed of a blink of an eye. This study attempts to understand this changed temporal experience of humanity. We begin with an analysis of the transformed experience of time and propose a need for the cultivation of phronesis to face the bubble of the now-time (Kozhamthadam, 2015). Next. We turn to the Grammatology of Derrida to examine how the new Digital world is writing (shaping)our life and thus invite us to trace critical ways of resistance. Finally, we take the new experience of time head and demonstrate that we have stopped thinking about what we are doing. We end with a conviction that it is only with the cultivation of thinking about what we are doing that we can respond to this new experience of temporality.

Hauntology of the Digital World of Images

Every invention, process, system or program includes its own disaster. This is a standard Hegelian doctrine. The inventors of the ship also invented the ship wreck. There are always seeds of destruction in everything. The fact that we have stepped into the internet era, we have recognised that it has blessings as well as curses. One of the issues that reveal to us the dark side of the web is that it traps us in the present moment. The moment that is now has become intensive and everything is compressed into it. Oral societies ran on a cyclical time and the literate ones ran on linear time. But something has drastically changed around us. We have entered what Gregory Ulmer calls electracy (Joseph, 1997). Electracy runs on the now-time. Everything happens in an instant. Most of our decisions on the net do not evolve deliberative thinking. They happen on the spot in an intense moment. This means our

decisions are based on intuitive beliefs that Malcolm Gladwell (2019) calls ‘blink’. We work in an instance of immediacy. My book, *Being Human in a World of Artificial Intelligence*, invites us to cultivate prudence that Aristotle calls *phronesis* so that our instantaneous or reflexive actions still stay ethical or moral. This means we need a new discipline of the mind that will enable us to deal with a culture that is trapped in a now-time.

Literacy is not just a technology of alphabets but is a school that forms our thinking as well as shapes our identity. We are fast moving away from the world of the alphabets and are gravitating towards the fast-paced dynamic digital world. Hence, we need a mode of classification of the digital images. It has to do with what the concept did to literacy. Concepts gave us ways of organizing things according to essences and accidents. Electracy needs an image category that will enable us to make decisions in the now-time. This is why I have argued that we need practical reason or *phronesis* to respond to the challenges of the now-time. Some scholars think that *phronesis* is thought in the future perfect tense and is concerned with what will have been. This means as prudence, it relies on the lessons of the past but finds creative ways of concretising those general principles in the present so that a future is hoped to be perfect. This means that the general or universal norm that is learnt from the past is to be applied case by case. In each case, the universal may modify differently to suit the specific condition. Such wisdom was called *phronesis* by Aristotle. *Phronesis* though a chief form of practical reason did not disassociate from the pure reason. It has been argued that dismantling of the relation between pure reason and practical reason began with the renaissance in Europe. With modernity, there came a slow death of practical reason. In fact, G.W. Leibniz praised the Chinese civilization for its superiority over the Western civilization in the area of practical reason (Horyna, 2020).

The now-time is intensely haunting us and the fact that we have no practical reason to assist us, we are heading towards a disaster. We have seen how fake news has instantaneously converted unsuspecting humans into lynch mobs. We are seeing a mass hysteria in political rallies where people and the politicians gather in large numbers without any fear of Covid-19. This mass frenzy as well as individual addictive attachments to the web show that we need to still find an ethical response to our life that is frozen into an intensive moment. We are indeed struck into ‘out of joint time’ that Derrida call’s aporia (Hart, 2007). Such time that is experienced as ‘out of joint’ actually opens our possibilities of being in the world. This is why we are haunted by the potentials of that time. Therefore, we need a new way of approaching the dance of images or the choreography of images in the internet. Ulmer suggests that *chora* (Greek word for space, since Plato) has a potency to be what topic has become for literacy. We can see how a topic becomes a choreography for related concepts in an organized constellation. This means the choreography of the images becomes an oracle that calls the individual on the web into being. We may understand it as a call or sense of being addressed with help of Luis Althusser who teaches us that we are interpellated subjects (Althusser, n.d).

Following Althusser, we can think that the dynamic choreography of sound, visual as well as verbal images say ‘Hey You’(address us) and hold our attention for a moment and we enjoy the dance of these images. But there are times when such images can lead us to a disaster like the way fake news converts unsuspecting humans into lynch murders. I like to think that the digital has become phygital (Welsh, 2021). We already have the internet of things. But more critically, the digital has come to become hybridized alongside our culture. This is why we can see how people succumb to mass propaganda and manipulations. The television debates on television are full of heat and no light nor insight. May be we can also see that it is for the reason stated above that people vote for notes. Usually notes come in the dead of the night and there is no time to think.

Pure reason has no room to guide the people so they mindlessly end up voting for notes inviting their own enslavement. The same is true about fanaticism where one has already surrendered his/ her mind to the narrow, narcissist, sadist and masochist beliefs. We can see such extremism visible in political popularism across the globe. This means that cyclic time and linear time has stopped influencing us. We are trapped in the now-time. Time stops for us; it becomes intense and offers us possibilities of being in the world. Trapped in a Now-time we cannot postpone our response. It has to be instantaneous. Our old ethical responses require us to undergo critical analysis. This requires time and we do not have this luxury. Lest our responses are driven only by our likes and dislikes (aesthetical tastes), we need to cultivate phronesis that will enable us to respond ethically and reflexively to our fast spaced yet paradoxically trapped in the now-time world.

Time for Grammatology: Decoding the Grammar and the Grammatics of Life

Derrida's method of deconstruction has paid rich dividends in circles of critical thinking. While its importance still remains, it may be important to enter his grammatology or the science of writing and examine its potency to critical thinking. Given the communicative technologies and the scope of the internet in our life, a return to grammatology (study of writings) is perhaps the most important and urgent turn that we have to take. This does not mean that deconstruction has reached a point of exertion and there is no light nor emancipative insight within it. While deconstruction has several fertile and critical applications, we turn to grammatology in order to deal with the play of signs in the world of digital images and the internet. To succeed in this effort, we have to turn to writing in its early stage. In order to perform this task, we have overcome blindness that reduces all writing to phoneticization. Derrida teaches that there is also

non-phonetic writings like pictorial, ideographic and symbolic (Scott, 2002). We can come to this realisation only when we enter the early stage of writing. We think that writing is associated with representation of the spoken word. In fact, this reduction of writing to spoken word leads us to consider to be phonic in nature. But this reduction actually limits the domain and power of writing. Even as we are conditioned by this reduction, contrary to our conditioning, the dynamic play of digital images on the internet has deconstructed this belief. Thus, to some extent, the world of the internet has crossed the limits of understanding of the role as well as the scope of writing.

In its early stages, writing was associated with drawing and visual art and had a loose association with speaking. It is the phoneticization of writing that transformed it into a representation of the spoken word alone. This means writing as representation repressed/suppressed its non-phonetic forms. Moreover, there cannot be exact one to one correspondence between the spoken word and the written word. This is because both carry ideographic/ cognitive forms as well as emotive/ affective inflections and hence are not merely verbal in nature. Phoneticization has to linearize writing to make it carry its ideographic forms. The world of digital media has already contested the phoneticization as well as linearization of writing. In many ways it has opened writing to its plural forms and in doing so has broken the chains that constrained our thought. Writing is enabled to embrace mythogram that is not subjected to successivity of the order of the logical time as well as irreversible temporality of the sound or the verbal language. Thus, we have to not only set writing free from speech, but we also have to set it free from its entanglements with phoneticization. Thanks to the dance of digital images in the world of the internet, we have already almost reached this stage. But some of us may be still be thinking that the world is flat even after it is circumnavigated.

Here we follow Derrida to expand the scope of writing so as to embrace the world of play of digital images. The consideration of non-phonetic writings makes room for the dance of signs in the digital world. We name as writing to all that gives rise to an inscription. This means the embrace of writing includes cinematography, choreography as well pictorial, musical and sculptural writings. We may include sport, military as well as political writings. This means grammatology opens us to these multidimensional forms of writings and thus deconstructs singularized, logocentric phonetic writing. Writing is a program. It seems to inundate all writing forms. We have to understand that gramme or graphme is a trace that inhabits all forms of writings both phonetic as well as non-phonetic ones. Hence, all of them can be studied by grammatology. This is why we have to accept that we have the challenge to understand and respond to the world of electracy through grammatology. The play of signs in digital media is a form of writing and can be decoded by following the principles of grammatology. But to fully understand what this dance of signs does to us, we have to enter into the energetics of trace which Derrida radicalizes by introducing Freud's slips of pen and tongue to full domains of writing. This is why choreography of the signs in the digital world produces a surplus and leaves an impact on us through its trace.

In several ways, many of us lament the end of the Book. The habit of reading is dying among people. This is chiefly because of the reign of non-phonetic writings. The libidinal investment in the form of reading has diminished and one can notice a great harvest of libidinal involvement of humans with the digital world. This is why grammatology has become an important key to understand how the new electronic media is writing us and shaping our life. We can be often blinded by the dance of the signs in the digital world and fail to understand how we are made to dance to its tunes. Grammatology as a science of

writing can reveal to us the writing of the images in the digital world as well as how that writing is writing our life. This means grammarology is a pedagogy. The fact that it manifests that the new media is writing our life, effectively enables us to wakefully resist it and take charge of writing our life. There is a difference between being written and writing one script of life. To do this we have to not just consider the cognitive/ideographic but also the energetic/ affective side of the dance of the signs in the world of digital media. This means we have to overcome the logocentrism of the digital world. The digital world, therefore, is messenger, message and massager. This means there are cognitive/ ideographic as well as emotive/ affective sides to the dynamism of the new media. What it does is important along with what it says. This is why we have to move from semiotic hermeneutics to productive hermeneutics. Grammarology includes both semiotic hermeneutics and productive hermeneutics. The rise of the dynamic digital world has hastened the importance of grammarology. To respond to this dance of sense, produced by the dance of sense, we have the challenge to embrace grammarology and see how it is at work everywhere writing the grammar of our life. Only once we move to grammarology, we will be enabled to take charge of not just the grammar but also the grammatics of our life.

New Experience of Time

Communication technologies have become omnipresent because of the smart phone. This condition has transformed our experience of time. Oral societies were based on cyclic time. The spoken word did not enjoy strict relations with the written word in such scenarios. The writing was in the form of drawings and hieroglyphs. The spoken word was very important. It

Communication technologies have become omnipresent because of the smart phone. This condition has transformed our experience of time.

being depended on the medium of sound, humans experienced irreversible temporality. This is because human spoken words cannot be recovered once spoken. They exist in an irreversible temporality. But when human words were alphabetized and came to be written, they were freed from the irreversible temporality but got chained to the order of the logic of linearity. We can read the written word and return to the same text again and again. We can see how the sacred texts of the religion are set free from temporal irreversibility but got entangled in linearity and logic that is different from the mythological thinking of the previous stage of humanity. This means with the new experience of time, we also have experienced a leap in our thinking. The written word ushered linear, rational and dialectical thinking while the previous thinking was cyclic and exhibits a different mode of rationality.

With the rise of electracy, (digital world), we have stepped into now-time of great intensity and speed. With this new experience of time, we have moved away from the irreversibility and linearity of time. Everything occurs in the now. We are now imprisoned in the futurism of the instant. The moment I have become pregnant with power and possibilities. Paul Virilio indicates that we are facing an information bomb. He says that the experience of space has also changed (Mambrol, 2018). The tyranny of distance has given way to the tyranny of real-time. We are living as disabled people, doing prosthetic gadgetry of all kinds. Because of this 'now' has almost replaced physical 'here'. Virtual space has come to replace real space. This is why Jean Baudrillard famously and provocatively said that the Gulf war was fought on computers (Wikipedia contributors, 2020). Not just real space has lost its importance, even physical bodies are being replaced by their avatars in the digital world. Erotics of distance is fast derailing human intimacy and attraction. What we are facing is the disappearance of materiality due to excessive digitalization and the hegemony of the now over

history and time of community. We are fast losing our links to our past and the future.

This means our experience of time has changed. We are no longer rigidly enslaved by irreversible and linear time schedules. We have become to embrace flexi-time. Flexi time or work schedules brings the best out of us. We are enabled to work optimally than those who are entangled by the dialectics of the irreversible and linear time. Maybe our attachments to the dialectics of irreversible and linear time refuses to see the change that surrounds us. Technological changes have indeed changed the experience of time. We experience reversible and non-linearity of time on our smart phones. We can rewind, stop and jump to the next item on our smart phone. Time has become elastic and we can stretch it in all direction as we live in a dynamic and intensive now. Some people have moved on with this changed time others are still pulling on with the irreversible and linear time. But moving on as well as staying on have their own costs.

Virilio tells us that virtualization is also invisibilisation (Dawes, 2019). When power becomes virtual it becomes invisible and almost omnipresent. This is why we have to understand how the virtual world has

When power becomes virtual it becomes invisible and almost omnipresent.

its power over us. While we are living in a now-time flowing at a great speed, we have less time to offer our responses and we almost are reduced to automatons who respond mindlessly and mechanically. This is the dark side of the loss of the irreversible and linear experience of time. This experience of time offered us refreshing and reflecting breaks so that we could critically discern our responses. The fast-paced digital world only allows for reflexive response and therefore, we have stepped into a new form of rationality and we may need what Aristotle called phronesis/practical wisdom. Since virtualization has invisibilized space, place

and even our bodies, we have a different mode of politics. We can see how parliament is silenced while mass political rallies as well television debate frenzies have become the order of the day. People are seen to cry slogans of their cultic leader in ecstasy. This means we are trapped in a now bubble and mindlessly support political agenda without knowing that social engineering is producing our responses.

It is important to realise that we are trapped in a bubble of now-time. The instant result culture had predisposed us while the rise of the internet and the communication technologies have imprisoned us into the now-time. We are now set to come full circle into logocentrism. Since we are liberated from both irreversibility and linearity, we are set free to hop in all directions of a focal moment that is now. Hence, it is urgent that we burst the time bubble before it explodes into our face. It has already destroyed our social life (family life) as we now prefer the next best thing to the face-to-face experience. Hence, we have to find ways of disengaging the now-time. Hannah Arendt had lamented that ‘we are losing our ability to think and speak of things nevertheless, we are able to do’ (Popova, 2017). Living in the now-time, we are fast becoming automatons. This is certainly a degradation and enslavement of our humanity.

The emerging world of digital communication technologies is threatening the possibility of politics

Virilio taught us that the emerging world of digital communication technologies is threatening the possibility of politics (Kellner, n.d) We are already seeing it in the form of hysteric masses around a cultic leader replacing debates in the parliament. But what is the way forward to us? It does appear that the way forward is through the internet and not outside it. We cannot change the reality that is around us. Gregory Ulmer certainly gives us the hope that our response to the tyranny of the now-

time is in the internet. What we need is a singular purpose that was set by Arendt in her book, *Human Condition*--- think what we are doing. Therefore, we cannot abdicate our ability to think what we do. Today, humanity needs it more than ever before.

Conclusion

Our study reveals to us that we cannot become passive spectators in our present world. We cannot simply worship a singular phallus and think that all is well in our world as the masses do with their cultic leader. We have to think about what we are doing. Giving up thinking is enslaving and dehumanizing. It is high time that we learn to think again.

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Totally Commitment to God and Fellow Human Beings: The Life and Message of Prof John Vattanky SJ

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Abstract: This article is an overview of the contribution of Prof John Vattanky, SJ, a pioneer in Indian philosophy. A logician and grammarian, Prof Vattanky has been rooted in his faith and tradition. He was a world authority on Navya-nyaya philosophy of Gangesa. The author also looks into his three fold passions in terms of Indian philosophy, logic and love and oriental traditions.

Keywords: Prof John Vattanky, Navya-nyaya, Gangesa, Logic and Love

With the passing away of Prof Dr John Vattanky, SJ, on Feb 22, 2012, the Church and the nation has lost an erudite scholar, a passionate lover and a visionary thinker. His critical or logical mind, coupled with his passionate heart, contributed significantly to a

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better understanding of the classical Nyaya and Navya-Nyaya schools making them relevant for our times! As a committed and devoted Catholic, he was open to the rich philosophical traditions of India. He interpreted this tradition, deepened it and made it available to contemporary scholars, both Indian and non-Indian, Hindu and non-Hindu.

Brief Biographical Sketch

Fr. John Vattanky was born on 03 July 1931 at Palackattumala in the Kottayam district of Kerala. His parents were Ulahannan and Mariam, and his siblings were Rose, Mariam, Anna, Joseph, Kuriakose and Thomas, none of whom are alive today. After his preliminary studies at Papal Seminary, Kandy, John joined the Jesuit Novitiate at Kozhikode on 27 November 1950 and took his first vows on 03 December 1952. He did his Jesuit Juniorate also in Christ Hall, Kozhikode, before proceeding for his philosophy studies at Sacred Heart College, Shembaganur (1954-1957). After completing his graduate studies at the University College, Trivandrum (1957-1959), he completed his theology at St Mary's College, Kurseong (1960-1964). He was ordained a priest on March 19, 1963 at Kurseong, West Bengal. After a period of teaching at Sacred Heart College, Shembaganur, he pronounced his final vows in 1968 at Campion Hall, Oxford (UK).

Initial Academic Life

After his priestly ordination, he taught philosophy at S.H. College, Shembaganur, Tamil Nadu, from 1965 to 66 and 1969 to 70. He took his M.A. in Oriental Studies at Oxford University from 1966 to 1969. He obtained his PhD in Indology from Vienna in 1974. Back in Kerala, he established the *Indology Institute* at St Xavier's College, Trivandrum, and as its Director, got immersed in research and writing. Later, in 1982, he shifted the Institute to De Nobili College, Pune rechristening it as *Centre for Advanced Indian Studies*. He also served as

Professor of Indian Philosophy at Jnana Deepa, Institute of Philosophy and Theology, Pune. He spent his sabbatical year pursuing his interest in Syriac Theology at Kottayam. In 2012 Fr John shifted his Institute to Kanjirapally in Kerala and continued his research in Indian Philosophy and Syriac Theology. In 2015, he suffered a stroke and became paralyzed. He was brought to Christ Hall, Kozhikode for better medical care and rest.

An Erudite Scholar, Writer and Teacher

The contribution of Fr John Vattanky to studies in Indian Philosophy has been recognized globally. His monumental work is *Gangesa's Philosophy of God* published in 1984. His other writings include *Development of Nyaya Theism* (1993), *Nyaya Philosophy of Language* (1995), and *A System of Indian Logic* (2003). There are many more academic articles through which he shared his intellectual height and affective depth with his colleagues.

Many of his colleagues and students would admire him working hard and listening patiently to the Indian scholars (*pandits*) and taking painstaking notes regularly and on a daily basis from 8:30 AM onwards. He had the remarkable stamina for hard and sustained intellectual work.

The classes he taught at Jnana Deepa were highly appreciated. He had the knack to simplify the abstruse philosophical concepts and make them relevant for the contemporary situation. As a teacher, he had been a mentor to generations of students, who have been inspired by his wisdom and intellectual acumen. Many of the privileged students would never forget the long hours of walk at the outskirts of Pune (Wagholi), which starts with a rosary and moves on to intellectual exchange and ends with a sumptuous and refreshing dinner. He was a man of self-discipline, regularity, punctuality, diligence and elegance.

We will peep into five of the significant books that Vattanky has authored. Through these books he has impacted the academic world, especially in Indian philosophy.

a. Gangesa's Philosophy of God

Gangesa's Philosophy of God (1984), a product of his persistent scholarship and genuine hard work discusses the proofs for the existence of God. It is not only a translation but also a thorough critical interpretation and evaluation of Isvaravada in Gangesa's monumental work, *Tattvacintamani*, an epoch-making work of Indian logic.

While discussing the issue of the existence of God, Vattanky, the world-authority on Navya-nyaya, has also raised a well-connected chain of issues in respect of

b. Development of Nyaya Theism

Vattanky's second book, *Development of Nyaya Theism* (1993), is a journey into Nyaya logic and epistemology. A key feature of this book is the manner in which the force of logic is made to bear upon the argument for the existence of God. While discussing the issue of the existence of God, Vattanky, the world-authority on Navya-nyaya, has also raised a well-connected chain of issues in respect of theism, some of which have far-reaching implications of logic, epistemology metaphysics, and ethics/religion.

c. Nyaya Philosophy of Language

Nyaya Philosophy of Language (1995) is yet another milestone in his contribution to the Nyaya Philosophy. With a view to making available the richness of thought contained in these works to all those who are interested in Indian Philosophy in general and in Navya-Nyaya in particular, Vattanky decided to translate the whole of *Karikavali*, *Muktavali* and *Dinakai* and interpreted them in the light of *Ramarudri* and *Subodhini*. This is pioneering and landmark work.

d. Karikavali

Kārikāvāli of Viśvanātha Nyāyapañcānana Bhaṭṭacārya (1997) is the translation with commentary of the Sanskrit text of Upamana and Sabda sections of Karikavali, Muktavali, and Dinakari. This is edited primarily with a view to helping the scholars who may like to study his previous work Nyaya Philosophy of Language systematically.

e. A System of Indian Logic

A System of Indian Logic: The Nyaya Theory of Inference (2003) is a translation and interpretation of the section on the inference of Karikavali, Muktavali and Dinakari. As Vattanky states in the preface, the intention of the book is “to present the actual contents of logic as developed in the Navya-Nyaya tradition.”

His Three-Fold Passions

What guided his philosophical quest and Christian reflection may be summed up in three of his enduring passions:

a. Passion for Indian Philosophy

His training at Oxford and Vienna prepared him to be an erudite and meticulous scholar, capable of long hours of serious and dedicated research. He had truly fallen in love with Indian philosophy and its nuanced interpretations. He was fully convinced of the relevance of classical Indian philosophy. That is why the first festschrift in his honour was aptly titled *An Indian Ending: Rediscovering the Grandeur of Indian Heritage for a Sustainable Future* (2013). It was remarkable that his book *Gangesa's Philosophy of God* was favourably appreciated by Kanchi Sankaracharya, who honoured him specially. It is this passion for his Indian roots that made him the most sought after Christian thinker among the secular or University circles in India.

b. Rooted in Logic and Love

A man of deep conviction, faith and devotion, Vattanky had a rigorous and inferential mind for philosophizing, especially the logic of Navya-nyaya system and equally heart for God and the people. His intellectual acumen brought him closer to the people, especially the weak and vulnerable. It is no wonder that the second volume in his honour was titled *Logic and Love: Reflecting on Professor John Vattanky's Contribution to Indian Philosophy and Spirituality*. He was both a logician and a lover who is devoted to simple spiritual practices like regular Eucharist, rosary and meditation with the depth of a mystic and vision of a profound Christian thinker. Truly he was a passionate lover of the Church, of India and the Indian philosophical system.

c. Open to Oriental Roots

Towards the last phase of his life, he had discovered the depth of Oriental theology and symbolism. After learning Syriac in his old age (2012), he studied the life and writings of St. Ephrem (306-373) and was truly enamoured by his symbolic theology, which he believed, fulfilled his mystical orientation. He was fond of giving the solemn blessings in Syriac with a sense of pride, belongingness and awe. Aware of and firmly rooted in his tradition, he opened himself to different sources of wisdom.

Living in the Presence of God

These three fold passions were fully founded on his undivided loyalty to the Divine. Vattanky firmly believed that it is only in the absolute that a human being is able to explain himself. According to Nyaya philosophy in general and Vattanky in particular, a “proper self-understanding of a human being is not possible without the absolute. In other words, a human being cannot understand himself properly except in the absolute; and so it follows inevitably that he is able to develop himself and

realize his full destiny only in a relationship with the personal God” (Karimundackal 2020: 92).

The living and loving God permeated every aspect of his being. As a genuine Christian and faithful Jesuit, he encountered God speaking to him in everything. “A God who is only real but who enters into the fabric of human existence intimately and profoundly is the starting point as well as the culmination of one of the major systems of Indian thought, namely Nyaya. The absolute of the Naiyayikas is a personal God to whom we owe allegiance and adoration. The best philosophical traditions of India, therefore, speak about a God who is real and who permeates the whole fabric of human existence” (Vattanky, 1983: 340).

Conclusion

Prof Vattanky passed away at 4.15 AM on Monday, 22 February 2021 at Christ Hall, Kozhikode, after being bedridden for five long years. He endured the suffering peacefully and never complained about his difficult times. He was ever thankful to his numerous caretakers and caregivers!

Vattanky was truly a passionate thinker, based on Indian tradition! He was a logician-lover, open to both reason and devotion. He was also open to his oriental roots, which did not limit him. It enabled him to open himself to others with a deep love for the Church, for the nation and for his traditions.

May the life and vision of Prof John Vattanky be an inspiration for us as Indian and Christians to be fully committed to our God, to the nation and the Church, so that we are fully human and fully divine! With our mind, heart and soul. He was indeed a scholar, believer and lover!

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Why the World Does Not Exist

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Gabriel, Markus. *Why the World Does Not Exist*. (translated by Gregory S. Moss) Malden, MA: Polity Press, 2015; pp. vi + 239; ISBN: 978-0745687575 \$28.00 (hardcover)

Markus Gabriel is best known for his popular writings in Philosophy especially in the field of New Realism. The title of the book evokes curiosity and interest. Although, this book has been published in the year 2013, originally in the German language (Gabriel, Markus. *Warum Es Die Welt Nicht Gibt*. 2013), it has not been discussed much in Indian philosophical circles. So, I thought of reviewing the book with the intention of wowing readers to enjoy this particular book. New Realism is basically a rejection of the thesis that there is no direct perception of the world. It opposes the view that we do not perceive the world directly but have only a representation of it. Contrary to this notion, New Realism argues that our thoughts about facts that exist about the world and the world itself have equal weight. Here lies the importance of Gabriel's book. Gabriel argues that the world does not

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exist, because to designate the world as an all-encompassing reality or as the domain of all domains, the world must stand outside beyond all the references of ordinary occurrences. We can never have such a comprehensive, objective perspective from the outside. Hence the world does not exist. Frames of references, or in his words, ‘domains’ or ‘fields of sense’ occur only with respect to other frames of references. The end result is an infinite regress. He says, “The principle that the world does not exist entails that everything else exists” (1).

Gabriel desires to free philosophy from the clutches of conceptual jargons. It is often popularly thought and believed when something expressed or articulated in simple terms, it does not have philosophical weight. Contrary to this thinking, Gabriel tries to express his views and new nuances in simple language, so that they could be understood by people who do not have much background in philosophy. Noteworthy in this context is the appendix in the book, in which the philosophical concepts which he had capitalized throughout the book is explained. However, I must say that the book is not so easy to understand for the common people.

He begins the book with a need for thinking philosophy anew. In order to find out how reality is, one must discard everything that is created or added in the process of knowing. The central tendencies of Metaphysics and Postmodernism have brought in more ‘green glasses’¹ rather than avoiding them (Gabriel borrows the same expression from Kant and says constructivist are prey to it). The basic thrust of his thesis developed from the main principle of New Realism to which he is very much devoted. “New realism assumes that thoughts about facts exist with the same right as the facts at which our thoughts are directed” (6).

¹ Immanuel Kant uses the metaphor ‘green glasses’. The general idea of the green glasses metaphor is that, we have all green glasses on. And they are part of our brains how do we view the world and lead us to believe that everything is green.

In the first three chapters, Gabriel tries to convince the reader logically about the title of the book. He builds up his thesis with a fundamental question: What does it mean for something to exist at all? The whole book rotates around this perennial question. Gabriel defines, “Existence= appearing in a field of sense” (see Chapter II, “What is existence?” 50ff). By field of sense, he means, a frame of reference, or domain in which a determinate object appears in a certain way. Stemming from the assumption that field of sense is a sense in which an object appears, it can be vague and colourful. Presumably, the field of sense could be understood as background conditions or a stage for occurrences. (Gabriel does not use the words ‘background conditions’ and ‘stage for occurrences’) (67-72). Thus, the final conclusion establishes that “We cannot grasp the world conceptually because there is no field of sense to which it belongs” (76).

Automatically, the world does not exist, then the question arises, does a God exist? What is the meaning of religion and life? He discusses such questions in the second part of the book through the themes like Religion, the Infinite, Science, Consciousness, Art, among others (See chapters iv, v, vi). He criticizes that the scientific world view has failed ontologically and epistemologically. It is worth noting, according to him, the mistake of science and religion consists in the setting of one ‘field of sense’ as the ultimate field of sense or looking for one single frame of reference as the ultimate all-encompassing one, although there are infinite fields of sense. He calls this trend fetishism. An exception to this, or an antidote is art (see Chapter VI, “The Meaning of Art,” 184 ff). He says: “All objects appear in specific ways; they are presented to us in different ways. Everything always appears in a certain kind of light. Because objects can be presented in many different ways they can belong to many different fields of sense” (192).

Readers may tend to feel baffled by the idea that the world does not exist, or there is no God in the sense of a ‘Supreme Object’, then, how could we account for a meaningful existence? Many aspects of infinite domains instead offer comfort, “Everything we know is an aspect of Infinite” (219). Furthermore, “We live together in infinitely many

fields of sense which we are always rendering intelligible in new ways. What more could we want?" (208).

Since the first part of the book deals with the central idea of the book and receives markedly different answers for the quest, the second part of the book may seem not as interesting as the first; however, Gabriel succeeds in pursuing the fundamental question of the book till the end.

What I appreciate most in Gabriel, is his simple way of writing, making philosophy not to be confined to the elite alone. He quotes extensively and his thought experiments and examples from daily life and from television series make him accomplish his aim, "that every expert is an expert to the extent to which he can also communicate to the layman" (His interpretation on Ludwig Wittgenstein's famous maxim, "whatever can be said can be said clearly" 159-160).

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It is most unlikely everyone will agree with everything. Gabriel says, however, he could bring a welcome freshness to New Realism, monumentally shifting the way we understand the world. I must say that this book offers a lot to unmask the assumptions of our time, leaving readers constantly questioning what is real as they consider: "World?"

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Finding God in Everything

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Pandikattu, Kuruvilla. *Finding God in Everything: Spiritual Insights to Finding Everything in God*. New Delhi, ISPCK.

Who are we? How can we relate to others and thereby realise ourselves? What is the meaning of my life? Where do we find God? How do we relate to Him? How does genuine spirituality enable me to become truly human, joyous and authentic?

These are some of the issues this book on contemporary, creative spirituality takes up. This book invites us to find God in everything. More, it invites us to find everything in God. It deals primarily with life as lived out in our daily lives in our interaction with things and God. Then it tries to draw spiritual insight from the events of daily life, so that we can live up our own lives, to embrace the world, fellow-human beings and God. The approach of this book is an inclusive and dialogical one, where we try to discern the divine in every aspect of earthly life.

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Each article in this book begins with a concrete experience, person, book or experiment. From that, we go to explore the larger dimensions of life and study the deeper values inherent in it. So, we move from the material to the spiritual, from the mundane to the perfect, without in any way sacrificing the material or the mundane.

Encountering fellow human beings, the world and the whole of reality face to face. The next part describes the role of stories in healing, liberating and making our lives genuinely humane.

The author believes that our spirituality emerges from the earthly, without in any way giving up the other-worldly. He holds that true joy and happiness comes from the simple pleasures of life. He hopes that our fulfilment as human beings starts from our concrete experiences of joy, sadness, relationships and love.

In the First Part of this book, he traces ways and means of reaching happiness and healing. He wants to show that our friends, relationships, memories and forgiving the harm others have done to us will enhance our well-being and bliss. The next Part talks of the spiritual dimensions of our day-to-day life, which allows us to experience genuine joy. Meditations, mindfulness and other means of spiritual experiences are treated.

The Third Part invites us to foster creativity through art, silence and music, which form part of the melodies of our lives. Here we realise that our spiritual life has been rooted in the earthly and bodily aspects of our lives. This takes us to the next Part, dealing with the spiritual practices leading to joy and optimism.

The abandonment that is critical to any spiritual life takes us to the next Part, nurturing the aesthetic dimension of our lives. Art,

dance, curiosity as well as reading and writing can make our life more authentic and empathetic. The Sixth Part helps us to explore some of the deepest human values and try to make the best of the encounters that we human beings are capable of: encountering fellow human beings, the world and the whole of reality face to face. The next part describes the role of stories in healing, liberating and making our lives genuinely humane.

Part Eight talks about our responsibility to society and the need to pay attention to the joys and sorrows of the larger political, scientific and social dimension of our collective reality. The next part deals with our responsibility to make this world a better one, recognising the larger (and at times, uncomfortable) truths of our social life.

The final Part talks about meaning and integrity within myself and in the larger world and cosmos we live in. It talks about the human need to be true to one's own self and to lead a modest and human life so that we can truly feel at home with ourselves.

Thus, the author shows through this book that the God we seek (or conversely and even better, the God who seeks us continuously) is to be found in everyone and everything. He is present everywhere and traces of Him can be found in all things at all times if we are attentive enough. That loving God always present to us. From this experience, everything and everyone gets a different value. Then everyone has to be seen in God and everything has to be experienced in the Divine. So, we are called to find Everyone and Everything in God. That is grace! Unconditional love and unqualified mercy.

This book argues that the spiritual can be traced in all activities, earthly, mundane and secular. It assumes that we can only reach the spiritual in and through the secular, the ordinary experiences of normal human beings. All in all, this is a modest attempt to reflect on our contemporary lives and see the glimpse or traces of the Divine in our lives. It is an invitation to discern God's presence in everything and everyone. It is a simple effort "to see God in everything." And further "to find everything in God" as St. Ignatius of Loyola would put it.

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In the foreword to this book Prof Stephane Baik, President of the Society of the Korean Society of Theology and Thought, Seoul, South Korea, congratulates "Professor Pandikattu for bringing out this book, I wish that the readers will gain deep spiritual insights, which are truly rooted in the Christian experience of God's unconditional love for each one of us."

This book is recommended to all those who seek to enliven their spirituality by discerning God in the ordinary things of life. A must for all religious houses and spiritual centres.

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